

Communication, Dissemination & Outreach Plan

For Project

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CC-BY = Creative Commons Attribution International License

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CORDIS = Community Research and Development Information Service

EU = European Union

INUO = University Institute for Research in Olive Groves and Olive Oils

MSCA-PF-EF = Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions European Postdoctoral Fellowship

OliPFUEL = Advanced biofuels production from waste olive pomace of olive oil industries

OTRI = Office for the transfer of research results, University of Jaén

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

PU = Public

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

STEM = Science, technology, engineering and mathematics

UJA = University of Jaén

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project number	101062601
Project name	Advanced Biofuels Production from Waste Olive Pomace of Olive Oil Industries
Project acronym	OliPFUEL
Call	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01
Topic	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01-01
Type of action	HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF
Service	REA/A/02
Project starting date	5 September 2022
Project duration	24 months
Net EU contribution	€ 165.312,96

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Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
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SUMMARY OF THE COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & OUTREACH PLAN

The Communication, Dissemination & Outreach Plan (Deliverable 1.3) is a part of the project “Advanced Biofuels Production from waste olive pomace of olive oil industries” that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under Marie Skłodowska Curie Postdoctoral fellowship with grant agreement No. 101062601. This document provides description of communication, dissemination, and outreach activities to different target audiences (e.g., Public, Students, Research community, Industries, and Policy makers). A summary of those activities is tabulated below.

Communication and outreach activities	Channels: European Researcher’s Night Programme, The Science Week Programme, UJA TV, CORDIS web platform, digital and print media, social media, and workshops
Dissemination activities	Publications of research article, datasets, and reports; Conferences participations; Workshop
Exploitation activities	Patent filing, Policy brief publication, Trademark or logo registration, Use of Horizon Results Platform
Legal obligations	Acknowledgment of EU funding and providing the OliPFUEL grant agreement id, open access peer reviewed publications under Creative Commons Attribution International License.

1. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

1.1 Introduction

The OliPFUEL project aims to demonstrate a more environmentally friendly process to produce advanced biofuels from waste olive oil from the olive oil industry. The present document explains the communication, dissemination, and outreach plan for the OliPFUEL project. This plan includes:

- Identifying different target audiences that could derive benefit from the outcome of the OliPFUEL project.
- Deciding appropriate channels and preparing suitable materials (e.g., documents, leaflets, posters, presentations, and videos) based on the requirements of target audiences for the communication, dissemination, and outreach activities.
- Fix proper timing for undertaking communication, dissemination, outreach, and exploitation activities based on the OliPFUEL project stage, results, and relevance to target audiences.

1.2 Main target audiences and expected impact

1.2.1 Policy makers

Reason for selection: Policy makers (EU and national) require information about new innovative technologies to develop regulatory frameworks and policies such as the Renewable Energy Directive, Net Zero 2050 climate targets, EU bioeconomy policy, EU green deal, etc.

Expected impact: The OliPFUEL process could be of interest to public authorities as it contributes to efficient waste resource utilisation, promoting bioeconomy, renewable energy use, and achieving climate targets.

1.2.2 Olive oil industry

Reason for selection: The olive oil industry has been facing a tremendous challenge to dispose of or reuse the environmentally toxic olive pomace slurry. Currently, the olive pomace mills have purchased olive pomace slurry from the olive oil industry to produce olive pomace oil and dried exhausted olive pomace pellets. But the major challenge is the storage and transportation of olive pomace slurry.

Expected impact: The OliPFUEL process advocates the in situ hydrothermal processing of the olive pomace at the olive oil industry, which not only reduces environmental pollution but also improves the profits of the olive oil industry and its workers.

1.2.3 Bio-based industry

Reason for selection: The European Union aims to accelerate the establishment and growth of bio-based industries to promote a self-reliant circular bioeconomy. Bio-based industries strongly depend on the abundant availability of non-edible waste biomass, preferably from point sources like the food industry. EU is the leading producer of olive oil, consequently generating a huge amount of olive pomace.

Expected impact: OliPFUEL develops a process for valorizing olive pomace to produce solid biofuel, bioethanol, and other biproducts. This process can be adapted by the existing bio-based industry and support the establishment of new biorefineries.

1.2.4 Research & Development community

Reason for selection: Hydrothermal processing and high-temperature fermentation are promising technologies to produce biofuels and bioproducts that are widely investigated by researchers all over

the world. However, many research gaps exist in those processes, and major advancements are required, such as reducing the use of expensive chemicals. Furthermore, many European researchers are focusing on investigating different approaches to valorising olive pomace waste and will benefit from any new innovations in this area.

Expected impact: One of the major goals of the OliPFUEL is to develop more environmentally friendly hydrothermal and fermentation processes to valorise olive pomace. The results could be of high use to other researchers to further advance these technologies.

1.2.5 Students

Reason for selection: Young students generally have a curious mindset and high potential for innovative ideas. However, they need the correct direction, motivation, and scientific exposure to choose a career in STEM and contribute towards solving global problems. This can also help them make decisions based on science, irrespective of their future career.

Expected impact: Sharing the significance and results of the OliPFUEL project with students aims to bring their attention to global problems, i.e., the importance of biofuels and the challenges faced by the olive oil industry, and use scientific research to find solutions to those problems. This would not only enhance their knowledge and scientific exposure, but also inspire them to become science-conscious citizens and pursue a career in research.

1.2.6 Public

Reason for selection: The public (citizens) has been the major victim of global problems like climate change and limited resource availability. They face lots of difficulties in their day-to-day lives to cope with those problems due to limited finances and resources. They pay taxes, which are used to fund research projects like OliPFUEL.

Expected impact: To create awareness and interest about the OliPFUEL project and its potential contribution to the improvement of their lives, such as self-reliance, indigenous local production of biofuel, saving the environment and public health, etc. In addition, inform them about EU policies and research funding schemes, and encourage them to know more about them.

2. COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The communication activities for OliPFUEL are planned by following the suggestions given in “Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” published by European commission. The communication activities will be performed on basis of the targeted audiences. In all the activities, simple language with clear project objectives and tailored materials will be used for effective communication with the targeted audiences.

The communication materials will be prepared beforehand and will be based on intended impact and expectation from audience. It will emphasize the importance and impact of OliPFUEL research in an easiest way possible (using infographics/brochure/press release/ videos) to the targeted audience. These materials will also highlight the EU policy (Renewable Energy) and programme (Horizon Europe) related to OliPFUEL research. The communication activities will continue throughout the project duration and will be extended even after the completion.

Communication materials and tools: Project website, print material and online tools such as posters, brochures, flyers, banners, online presentations, interactive infographics, recorded interviews, project factsheets, presentations, and project process demonstration.

In the OliPFUEL project, some data deposition and sharing will be withheld until the decision made about patent filing and obtaining clearance from the Intellectual Property Rights Office, University of Jaén (UJA), Spain.

Information about the OliPFUEL project and its results has been regularly shared with the target audiences, which are tabulated in the subsequent sub-sections below.

2.1. Completed activities

Timing	Target Audiences	Channels	Activity
26 August 2022	Researchers, Industry, Policymakers	Online CORDIS (European commission); Weblink: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101062601 ; One-way communication	Publishing all information related to OliPFUEL project
5 October 2022	Senior Citizens	Face to Face presentation (Two-way communication).	Performed under “Technology and engineering keys to the progress of society, university program for seniors,” Session 1, Chemical and environmental engineering, University of Jaén.
20 October 2022	Researchers	Online shared on Research Gate (Two-way communication).	OliPFUEL general information
24 and 26 October 2022	Olive oil Industry	Face to Face meeting (Two-way communication).	Discussion on OliPFUEL project and potential collaboration opportunities.
8 November 2022	Public, Students, Researchers	Online sharing on university of Jaen (UJA) website and YouTube channel (One-way communication): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://tv.ujaen.es/video/6385f25c8f42080c738b456c • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9bMTa0336HI • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MOgRCx_kL9Q 	Interview about OliPFUEL taken and shared by UJA Investiga team and SER radio Jaén of the University of Jaén.
17 November 2022	Students	Face to face presentation (Two-way communication) followed by online sharing (One-way communication). Weblink: https://www.infolinares.com/4-500-estudiantes-secundaria-participado-actividades-organizadas-uja-semana-ciencia/	Participation in “The Science Week Programme” of University of Jaén., Presentation done on OliPFUEL: Magic of Waste to Products, participation of approx. 120 secondary school students of Jaén province.
22 November 2022	Researchers, Industries	Online sharing (One-way communication): http://www.secheresse.info/spip.php?article122496	OliPFUEL brief information published in multiple languages on EU supported web portal
1 December 2022	Students, Researchers	Online sharing (One-way communication) by the University of Jaen website. Weblink: https://diariodigital.ujaen.es/investigacion-y-transferencia/la-uja-lidera-el-proyecto-olipfuel-para-la-generacion-de	Article on “OliPFUEL’ for the generation of biofuels from the olive oil industry” published by digital diary (boletín) and University Institute for Research in Olive Groves and Olive Oils (INUO) of the University of Jaén.

		<p>https://inuouja.com/en/2022/12/05/inuo-leads-the-olipfuel-project-for-the-generation-of-biofuels-from-the-olive-oil-industry/</p>	
1 -3 Dec. 2022	Public	<p>Online newspapers (One-way communication). Selected weblinks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europapress.es/andalucia/andalucia-verde-01334/noticia-uja-lidera-proyecto-olipfuel-generar-biocombustibles-partir-industria-aceite-oliva-20221201120103.html • https://cronicadeandalucia.com/economia/olipfuel-generacion-biocombustibles-universidad-jaen/ • https://www.ideal.es/jaen/jaen/lidera-proyecto-crear-20221201122538-nt.html • https://vivajaen.es/jaen-local/1135444/la-uja-lidera-un-proyecto-para-generar-biocombustible-a-partir-de-la-industria-del-aceite-de-oliva/ • https://www.oleorevista.com/texto-diario/mostrar/4094557/nuevo-proyecto-generacion-biocombustibles-partir-residuos-industria-aceite-oliva • https://www.asajajaen.com/actualidad/proyecto-para-la-generacion-de-biocombustibles-a-partir-de-la-industria-del-aceite-de-oliva • https://www.agrodiario.com/texto-diario/mostrar/4095275/generan-biocombustibles-residuos-industria-aceite-oliva • https://www.ondacerojaen.es/inicio/la-uja-lidera-el-proyecto-olipfuel-para-la-generacion-de-biocombustibles-a-partir-de-la-industria-del-aceite-de-oliva 	<p>Online articles on OliPFUEL published by several digital newspapers such as Europa press, Cronica de andalucia, Ideal, Viva Jaén, Oleo revista, Asaja Jaén, Onda Cero Jaén.</p>
2 December, 2022	Public	<p>Print and digital newspaper (Two-way communication). Weblink: https://www.diariojaen.es/jaen/investigacion-para-generar-del-aceite-biocombustible-CY876070.</p>	<p>OIPFUEL information published by Dairio Jaén, a print and digital newspaper</p>

5 December 2022	Energy sector		Digital publication (One-way communication) Weblink: https://new.energias-renovables.com/bioenergia/la-uja-investiga-la-generacion-de-biocombustibles-20221205	OIPFUEL information published by Renewable Energy Magazine.
12 Decemeber 2022	Public		Online sharing in social media (two-way communication).	OliPFUEL post shared in LinkedIn, X, and Facebook
10 January 2023	Public		Online video sharing (One-way communication).	Interview about OliPFUEL project information by 7 TV Vivir Linares, a digital news channel.
8 February 2023	Students		Face to face presentation and workshop (Two-way communication).	OliPFUEL presentation at Geolith Scientific Campus, University of Jaen to promote school student's participation under Day of Women and Girls in Engineering Programme. Attended by at least 40 students.
5 May 2023	Students		Face to face presentation and workshop (Two-way communication).	OliPFUEL presentation and workshop for graduate students of University of Jaén at Linares Science and Technology Campus.
10 May 2023	Olive Sector		Revista Almaceite - Print and online magazine (One-way communication). Weblink: https://revistaalmaceite.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/anuario-aove-olivar-espanol-2023.pdf	Published general article on OliPFUEL: OliPFUEL aims to obtain by-products for the food, pharmaceutical or cosmetic industry" in Anuario AOVE 2023 magazine.
29 September 2023	Public, Researchers	Students,	Face to face presentation and workshop (Two-way communication).	European Researcher Night - 2023 Participation at Linares, organised by the University of Jaén.
23 – 27 October 2023	Researchers		Face to face discussion (Two-way communication).	Participation in PhD course Industrial Biotechnology for Lignocellulose Based Processes" Chalmers University of Technology, Gotenburg, Sweden
30 November 23	Students		Face to face presentation and workshop (Two-way communication). Weblink: https://ieshuartedesanjuan.es/departamentos-didacticos/area-cientifico-tecnologica/fisica-y-quimica/visita-a-la-escuela-politecnica-2-o-bachillerato	OliPFUEL presentation and workshop for school students of IES Huarte De San Juan at Linares Science and Technology Campus, University of Jaén. Attended by 15 students.
22 December 2023	Public		Social media (One-way communication). Weblink: https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=658732816449715&set=a.220070506982617	Sharing OliPFUEL information by Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions social media handles.

December 2023	Olive sector	Print magazine (One-way communication).	Sharing general article on OliPFUEL: Production of advanced biofuels from olive pomace derived from olive oil production, Published by ALDABA Magazine, December 2023 edition (pp.87-88).
6 June 2024	Researchers	Leaflet distribution and face to face interaction with other researchers (Two-way communication).	Participation in the dissemination activity of SCALE-Up project (funded by the European Union) organised by Corporation Technology of Andalusia at Higher Polytechnic School Linares, University of Jaén.
13 June, 2024	Olive sector	Revista Almaceite - Print and online magazine (One-way communication). Weblink: https://revistaalmaceite.com/anuarios-aove-espanol/	Published general article on OliPFUEL: OliPFUEL aims to obtain by-products for the food, pharmaceutical or cosmetic industry” in Annual AOVE 2024 magazine.
10 June 2024	Public, Researchers	Online sharing (Two-way communication) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380993487_Industrial_Two-Phase_Olive_Pomace_Slurry-Derived_Hydrochar_Fuel_for_Energy_Applications • https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380661081_Fermentation_of_Sugar_by_Thermotolerant_Hansenula_polymorpha_Yeast_for_Ethanol_Production • https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=436803625882253&set=a.133137982915487 • https://www.linkedin.com/posts/adnan-asad-karim-phd-166829a6_industrial-two-phase-olive-pomace-slurry-derived-activity-7205978375360798720-JECR?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop 	Publication from OliPFUEL project shared in social media.

2.2. Future activities

The planned communication and outreach activities to be done are tabulated below.

Timing	Target Audiences	Channels	Activity
27 September 2024	Public, Students, Researchers	Face to face presentation and workshop (Two-way communication).	European Researcher Night - 2024 Participation to share information about OliPFUEL.
October 2024 (Tentative)	Public, Students, Researchers	Online sharing (partial two-way way communication)	OliPFUEL concluding results will be shared through the help of SER radio, University of Jaén and social media channels.
November 2024 (Tentative)	Students, Researchers	Open workshop (Face to face presentation), Two-way communication	An open workshop will be conducted at Linares Science and Technology campus, University of Jaén for stakeholders like public, researchers, industries, NGOs etc.
November 2024	Women	Online sharing through web platform (https://www.globalwomennet.org/) . Two-way communication	OliPFUEL results and associated publications will be shared with women researchers like the Global Women's Network for the Energy Transition (GWNENET, Vienna, Austria), Earth Science women network, The European network of mentors for women entrepreneurs.
Post January 2025 (tentative)	Industries	Online sharing (One-way communication)	OliPFUEL project results shared with local olive oil industries, and biofuels industry through specific websites like EU agenda, Renewable Energy Magazine, Revista Almaceite Magazine, ALDABA magazine, and NGOs websites etc. In this task, help of The University Institute of Research on Olive and Olive Oils (INUO), University of Jaén could also be taken.
Post January 2025 (tentative)	Public	Face to Face presentation and interaction (Two-way exchange)	Participation in seminars and social forums organised by City council linares/Jaén or NGOs

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The OliPFUEL research results and findings will be shared with the potential users such as scientific community, olive oil industries, biofuel industries, and policy makers through both online platforms (like EC websites, University websites, and social media channels) and offline events/meetings. Activities for disseminating the results of OliPFUEL has been done through open access peer reviewed publications of research article, datasets, and reports, as well as giving presentations in the conferences. Details of these dissemination activities are described in following subsections.

3.1 Completed activities

3.1.1 Published research articles

- Industrial Two-Phase Olive Pomace Slurry-Derived Hydrochar Fuel for Energy Applications. *Polymers* 2024, 16, 1529. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16111529>. Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/11353931>
- Fermentation of Sugar by Thermotolerant *Hansenula polymorpha* Yeast for Ethanol Production. *Fermentation* 2024, 10, 260. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation10050260>. Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13144682>

3.1.2 Participation in the congress

- Oral presentation on “Sustainable Hydrothermal Carbonisation of Industrial Olive Pomace Using Inherent Water Content to Produce Hydrochar for Fuel Application.” 32nd European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (EUBCE), 27th June, 2024, Marseille, France. Weblink: <https://programme.eubce.com/abstract.php?idabs=20865&idses=1717&idtopic=20>; Accessed on 18 July 2024.
- Poster presentation on “*Hansenula Polymorpha* Yeast Driven Fermentation of Pure Sugars for Alcohols Production.” 32nd European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (EUBCE), 25th June, 2024, Marseille, France. Weblink: <https://programme.eubce.com/abstract.php?idabs=21309&idses=1624&idtopic=23>; Accessed on 18 July 2024.
- Oral presentation on “*Hansenula polymorpha* application for production of advanced biofuels.” Final Open Meeting of the YEAST4BIO (CA18229), funded by European Union under COST Action (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) programme, 9-10 April 2024, Mostoles (Madrid), Spain.
- Oral presentation on Success story at University of Jaén: OliPFUEL; Information seminar on the Horizon Europe - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Postdoctoral Fellowships Programme 2024, 18/04/2024, Organised by International Projects Office, Office of the Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer, University of Jaén, Jaén Province, Spain.

3.2 Future activities

3.2.1 Conference: Participation in the 33rd European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (EUBCE)-2025, Valencia, Spain to share complete results of OliPFUEL project regarding valorisation of olive pomace slurry for production of advanced biofuels and other bioproducts.

3.2.2 Research article:

- Publication of article on production of hydrochar fuel by microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application (currently under review in *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*).

- Publication (article submission tentatively by 30 January 2025) of research article with tentative title: Sustainable Integrated process for Olive pomace valorisation to produce bioalcohols and other bioproducts.

3.2.3 Datasets publication:

The datasets and relevant experimental information related to OliPFUEL results will be published in the Zenodo repository as per open science policy.

3.2.4 Technical report: Publication of technical report of OliPFUEL project on EU cordis website after 4 November 2024.

3.2.5 Non-technical article: Disseminating the OliPFUEL results in simple language for citizens and other stakeholders using EUagenda web platform (<https://euagenda.eu/>).

3.2.6 Portal of the research, University of Jaén: Digitally store and publicise the OliPFUEL results and associated publications through Portal of the research, University of Jaén (<https://investigacion.ujaen.es/resultados>).

4. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

The exploitation activities would be conducted to utilise the OliPFUEL results for commercial and societal benefits. Some of these main activities are described as follows.

4.1 Trademark or name registration

Application to secure copyright for “OliPFUEL” name is processed on 21/05/2024 through Technology Transfer Manager, Office for the Transfer of Research results (OTRI), University of Jaén.

4.2 Potential patent filing

After obtaining the full results of OliPFUEL project and evaluating its commercialisation potential, decision will be taken to file a patent with tentative title of Integrated process for production of olive pomace slurry derived bioproducts. In case of positive decision, the patent will be filed (possibly by December 2024) with the help of Office for the transfer of research results (OTRI), University of Jaén.

4.3 Policy brief

A policy brief document will be prepared to highlight OliPFUEL results and its practical significance towards improving socio-economic conditions. This document will be submitted to the Ciencia en el Parlamento, Spain. It would also be shared widely through online media.

4.4 Horizon Results Platform

The customised support of Horizon Results Platform (European Commission) could be used for exploiting the results of OliPFUEL for securing industrial collaboration to benefit market and society.

5. LEGAL OBLIGATIONS

Research outputs (e.g., peer reviewed research articles, datasets) and communication materials (e.g., leaflets, posters, information sheets, videos, etc.) will be published open access. These will be freely available to the public under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY). The published research article, datasets (Zenodo repository, based on FAIR principles), and reports will contain a persistent identifier (like a DOI number) and suitable metadata.

In all the published materials related to the OliPFUEL project, acknowledgement of EU support, the European flag (emblem), and a funding statement with a grant agreement ID will be provided. In addition, a disclaimer will also be given with the following statement: “Funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”